

IMPACT OF COLLEGIAL TEACHING AND VERBAL INTERACTION ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN BIOLOGY AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS, SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of collegial teaching and verbal interaction on academic performance in biology among Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The research used quasi experimental control group design involving pretest and post-test for the study. N objectives, nine research questions and nine null hypotheses guided the study. Three co-educational secondary schools with 204 SSII Biology students (118 boys and 86 girls) were randomly selected out of the eight co-educational schools with 1576(891 boys and 685 girls) SS II Biology students as the target population. Two schools were subjected to three experimental groups where Biology concepts were taught to the students employing collegial teaching using high and low verbal interaction. The third group was taught using lecture method as the control group. Two instruments, Biology Academic Performance Test (BAPT) with reliability co-efficient of 0.89 and Attitude of Students towards Biology Questionnaire (ASTBQ) with reliability co-efficient of 0.86 were used to collect the data for pretest and post-test and to test the nine null hypotheses. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistic, Anova and t-test at a significant level of $P \leq 0.05$. One of findings of the study was that students in collegial teaching method performed better than those taught using lecture method when the same concepts are taught by teachers using high, medium and low verbal interaction. The conclusion from this study was that if teachers collegiate among themselves and allow active participation of students dominating discussion during lesson, then we should expect improved performance in Biology. It was therefore recommended that Biology teachers should employ collegial teaching method and encourage high teacher-student interaction.

Keywords: Collegial teaching, Verbal interaction, Academic performance and Biology

Introduction

Biology as designed by the curriculum planners is to be taught by a

single expert in the subject. But experience has shown that every biology teacher in the senior secondary school do

take side with specific aspects of the subject (Ajayi, 2016). This is because the teachers are trained in particular science discipline like Biology, Zoology, Botany etc, therefore there are lots of biases. Being bias in specific aspects of the subject in which the attainment of designer's objectives in the subject might not be achieved. Alausa, (2001), asserted that, there are challenges when some topics taught at Secondary School could not be handled by the teacher of biology.

Teaching of biology is a challenging work for the biology teachers. While teaching the biology concepts in classroom, teachers are often faced with many difficulties. Studies conducted on science education indicate that teachers' qualification and teaching experience are responsible for their perception of the difficulty. Studies have also revealed that some Biology concepts are abstract and therefore difficult to comprehend for teachers, (Albert, 2002).

Finely, Harwell, (2003), were of the opinion that, once teachers have difficulty in understanding certain biology concepts, they will not be able to teach such concepts to the students rightly. There is, therefore, likelihood that some aspects of the subject will be left partially taught or not taught at all. The challenge has further been aggravated by teachers' interest and attitudes towards the subject.

Shuaibu and Usman (2002) and Alausa (2007) equally asserted that the type of method usually adopted in teaching biology affects students' academic performance, The lecture or expository method of teaching does not give students the desired opportunity to express themselves well and it equally limits interaction between students-students, and teacher- students' interaction (Usman, 2007). During the course of such interactions, students' fears and anxieties are not addressed in the class. For effective teaching and learning of biology, it is expected that students participate actively in the process by asking questions, holding discussions, carrying out class activities and making generous intellectual contributions. The biasness of teachers does not encourage interactions coupled with high population of students in classrooms.

Situations where teachers work as colleagues to share and develop professional practices together (collegial learning) have been found to check the effects of subject biases which leads to teachers skipping some concept and it effects the academic performance of students (Aronso, 2014). It is against this background that collegial teaching and verbal interaction will be experimented and their impact on students' performance and attitudes towards biology

assessed. The following research questions were formulated for this research:

- i. What is the difference in Academic performance of students taught biology using high level of verbal interaction and those taught employing lecture method?
- ii. What is the difference in Academic performance of students taught biology using low level of verbal interaction and those taught using lecture method?
- iii. What is the difference in Academic performance of students taught Biology using high level of verbal interaction employing collegial teaching and those taught using low level of verbal interaction?

Literature Reviewed

Collegial teaching is usually an ongoing programme in schools. It is seen as a professional development of teachers to deepen their classroom practices or teaching skills. One of the theories underpinning collegial teaching is called organizational theory. According to Taylor (2007), organizational theory represents the merger of scientific management, bureaucratic theory and administrative theory. The theory deals with the study of organizations for the benefits of identifying common themes for the purpose of solving problem, maximizing efficiency and productivity, and meeting the needs of

stakeholders.

Barzilai, (2010), explained further that organizational theory can be classified into three broad concepts which includes: individual processes like motivation theory, group processes including working in groups/ communication and power to influence what we say and do, and organizational processes, as it relates to organizational structure. Organizations like schools can play a role in developing their staff for success by organizing workshops, and seminars that focus on developing organizational success. Allowing for a diverse set of experiences with appropriate support can maximize and expand the capabilities of each teacher.

When team learn together, Senge, (2009) suggest that not only there can be good results for the organization; members will grow rapidly than could have occurred otherwise. Collegial learning starts with dialogue, which is the capacity of members of a team to suspend assumptions and enter into a genuine thinking together as colleagues; this is the spirit of collegiality. In such a climate, there is a free flowing of ideas and insight not attainable individually. It equally helps team members recognize the pattern of interaction that brings about improved learning outcome in terms of performance. So, this research is built around organizational theory of

teachers relating well by joint planning, share teaching and joint reflection/feedback of what happens in class.

Empirical Review

A review on collegial teaching, verbal interaction as well as academic performance was made by several authors. Ubah (2005) worked on the effect of collegial teaching on students' achievement in Further Mathematics. A sample of 160 Junior Secondary School students selected from four coeducation schools in Onitsha and Nnewi educational zones in Anambra state was used. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The data collected were analyzed based on each research question and hypotheses by computing the mean score, standard deviation and analyses of covariance (ANCOVA) with the pre-test scores as covariance at $p \leq .05$ probability level. The result showed that students taught through Team Teaching Strategy had a better achievement than students taught through conventional Strategy. It was recommended that mathematics teachers should teach further mathematics using collegial Teaching Technique. The findings revealed that collegial teaching instructional method is more effective than the conventional method as regards the academic achievement. One of the possible reasons for this is that collegial

teaching is a co-operative system of instruction where two or more teachers collegiate together to share the same subject matter. The findings are in line with Karin (2000), who stated that collegial teaching is used in increasing the students' level of understanding and retention, in addition to enabling the students to obtain higher achievement. He further reported that as a result of the collegial teaching, the students received more individualized attention from more experienced teachers. The cooperation students observed between the team teachers serves as a model for teaching students positive teamwork skills and attitudes. Unlike the conventional method of teaching which does not permit active participation of learners.

Usendia and Effiong (2015), conducted research on verbal interaction patterns and Junior secondary students' performance in Basic science and technology in Uyo, Akwa Ibom, Nigeria. The study investigated the effects of dominative and integrative classroom interaction (adopting Flanders' and Eggleston's interaction Analysis category system checklist to measure teacher-students verbal interaction in the classroom, high, medium and low interaction) patterns on the performance of basic science and technology students considering teacher's qualifications and teacher's years of experiences and

teacher's gender. The study was quasi-experimental research conducted in Uyo Local Government, Akwa Ibom Nigeria. 994 JSII students comprising 420 males and 574 female students and 20 JSII Basic Science technology teachers selected from 10 public co-educational schools. Criterion sampling technique formed the study sample. Two researches made instruments, Basic Science and Technology Performance Test (BSTPT) with reliability co-efficient 0.75 and Teachers Classroom Interaction Analysis Checklist (TCIAC) adapted from Flanders Interaction Analysis Category System Checklist (FIACSC) with intra item reliability co-efficient of 0.80 and 0.75 were used in collecting data. Data generated were analyzed using t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The findings indicated a significant influence of teachers' classroom interaction patterns on students' performance with students in integrative classroom performing significantly better than those in the teacher dominated classes. The outcome shows teachers in senior secondary schools collegiate and allowed high level of verbal-interaction. It also showed that some types of classroom interactions can have a positive effect on various outcomes such as academic development, achievement and attitudes towards learning science.

Ayodele and Olatunbosun (2015), investigated gender differences in performance on students towards Biology in SS in Ekiti State Nigeria using a descriptive survey research method. 300 SS II students were selected from 12 public schools across the state made up of 160 males and 140 females using multistage random sampling technique. Two instruments namely Scientific Attitude Inventory II (SAI) and Biology Achievement Test (BAT) was used for the analysis of data. SAI and BAT had a reliability of 0.78 and 0.89 respectively. Data were analyzed using inferential statistics such as Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis. The study revealed that there was significant difference in students' gender and performance in biology. Boys tend to dominate classroom talk and there is evidence to suggest that teachers deliberately gear the content of lessons toward boys' interest in order to retain attention and control. Teachers tend to interact more with male students than females.

Based on the above review, it is sufficient to say that there is enough of empirical evidence on the positive impact of collegial teaching with verbal interaction on academic performance among biology senior secondary school's students. However, these studies were

conducted in different settings from that of the present research.

Methodology

Quasi experimental design was adopted for this research. The design enabled comparison between treatments versus control conditions on participants. This design was used to examine the impact of Collegial Teaching on students' performance and attitudes toward biology when they were taught by teachers using different levels of teacher- student verbal interaction for both experimental and control groups. There were high level verbal interaction (HVI) and low-level verbal interaction, (LVI). The treatments comprises two groups which were subjected to high and low level verbal interaction while control group comprises one group respectively.

The Senior Secondary II (SS II) Students of 2019/2020 session from Sokoto Educational Zones formed the subjects of this study. Two co-educational schools were selected through stratified random sampling method from the seven local governments that are part of the educational zone. This was done to allow wide and equal representation of each local government. Three classes were formed as the sample for the study. These schools are GDSS Gagi, GDSS Dange, Shuni and GDSS Gatawa. Two

schools out of the three forms the experimental groups while the last school forms the control group. Each class in each school was handled by two teachers who are trained on Collegial Teaching using Eggleston Science Teaching Observation Schedule aspects of verbal interaction. To select teachers that were engaged in Collegial teaching strategy for high, medium and low-level verbal interaction from the three treatment schools, first the researcher demonstrated through teaching some lessons using the three levels of verbal interaction to the school teachers. For the purpose of this research, 'intact classes' of SSII biology students were used as the sample size. The total number for the four schools sampled was two hundred and seventy-one (204), made up of 118 males and 86 females' students.

The instrument used was Biology Academic Performance Test. The Biology Academic Performance Test (BAPT) was developed by the researcher. The Biology Performance Test was administered to biology teachers who served as research assistance, consisted of 40 objective items covering the whole Biology syllabus especially topics treated in SS II. Some of the questions were picked from past questions on SSCE SSII syllabus and on the same topics in SS II curriculum. The test items were given to some experts who were

specialized on these aspects. Among them were experts in Science Education Department Faculty of Education, Sokoto State University, and Professors and senior lecturers who are well experienced in test construction in the department of Science and Vocational Education and faculty of education Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. The test items were also given to a panel of senior science teachers who teach in the upper biology level from different secondary schools to validate of the instrument.

The reliability of Biology Academic Performance Test (BAPT) was determined by conducting the test with the designed instruments Two test in a test-retest administration were conducted. The scores obtained were then subjected to test for reliability index and internal consistency coefficient for the items within the instruments using Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC). The observed reliability for BAPT was found to be 0.89.

Data were collected from the pre-test and post-test respectively. The pre-test consists of Biology Academic Performance Test (BAPT), while the post-test data was collected at the end of the treatment using Biology Academic Performance Test (BAPT). This was conducted by the researcher and researcher's assistants. All tests were

administered and data were collected on the spot to avoid missing results. The result was collected and recorded for analysis based on experimental and control of verbal interaction and academic performance between males and females' students.

Results and Discussion

This section analyzed data in accordance with the research objectives and hypotheses.

Null Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students taught Biology using collegial teaching at high level of verbal interaction and their counterparts taught using lecture method.

Table 1: Significant Difference in Performance between HVI and LM

Groups	N	Mean	SD	F	Df	p-value	Decision
EG1	74	25.08	5.19	106.87	1 (161)	0.001	Ho Rejected
CG	72	16.90	4.68				

$\alpha \leq 0.05$

Source: Field Data, 2021

Result in Table 1 shows that there is significant difference in performance between students taught biology using high verbal interaction and those taught using lecture method. There was a significant difference between the two groups ($F = 106.87$; $p\text{-value} < 0.05$), with students who were taught using HVI

performing significantly better than those taught using lecture method. In view of this, the research hypothesis was therefore rejected, implying that students taught biology using HVI differed significantly in their academic performance with their counterparts taught using lecture method.

Null Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students taught Biology using collegial teaching at low level of verbal interactions and their counterpart using lecture method.

Table 2: Significant Difference in Performance between LVI and LM

Groups	N	Mean	SD	F	Df	p-value	Decision
EG2	58	17.22	4.49	0.14	1 (145)	0.70	H ₀
CG	72	16.90	4.69				Accepted

$\alpha \leq 0.05$

Source: Field Data, 2021

Table 2 shows the significant difference in performance between students taught biology using low level of verbal interaction of collegial teaching method and those taught using lecture method. From the analysis, there is no significant difference in performance between the two groups ($F = 0.14$; p -value > 0.05). Based on this, the research hypothesis was therefore accepted, suggesting that students' performance did not differ significantly even when they were exposed to low verbal interaction.

Null Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students taught Biology using high level of verbal interaction employing collegial teaching and those taught using low level of verbal interaction.

Table 3: Significant Difference in Performance between HVI and LVI

Groups	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	p-value	Decision
HVI	74	25.08	5.19	8.147	104	0.001	H ₀
LVI	58	17.22	4.49				Rejected

$\alpha \leq 0.05$

Source: Field Data, 2021

Result presented in Table 3 shows significant difference in academic performance between students taught biology using high verbal interaction of collegial teaching method and those taught using low verbal interaction. There was a significant difference between the two groups of students in terms of their academic performance ($t = 8.14$; p -value < 0.05). The research hypothesis was therefore rejected, implying that students who were taught biology using high verbal interaction of collegial method significantly performed better than their counterparts who were taught using low verbal interaction.

Summary of Major Findings

Findings of the study are summarized in accordance with the research hypothesis as follows:

1. There was a significant difference between students taught biology using HVI and those taught using lecture method ($F = 106.87$; $p\text{-value} < 0.05$), with students who were taught using HVI performing significantly better than those taught using lecture method.
2. There was no significant difference in performance between students taught biology using LVI and those taught using lecture method ($F = 0.14$; $p\text{-value} > 0.05$).
3. There was a significant difference in terms of academic performance between students taught biology using high verbal interaction and those taught using low verbal interaction ($t = 8.14$; $p\text{-value} < 0.05$).

Discussion of Findings

This section further discussed the findings of the study. Three major significant findings were made.

First, a significant difference in terms of academic performance was observed between students exposed to high verbal interaction of collegial teaching method and those exposed to lecture method. However, no significant difference was noticed for the low verbal interaction group. This suggested that collegiality is only beneficial at the highest level. A number of explanations have been offered as to why high verbal

interaction of collegial method is significant in improving students' performance, including the fact that it creates an avenue for students' practice; eliminates passivity, boredom and absent mindedness in the class; encourages active participation; and the fact that each student participant influences the behavior of other students thereby conditioning them to fully participate in classroom activity (Biyi, 2001; Olagide, 2002; Olu, 2004).

Thus, from the findings, it appears that high verbal interaction of collegial method is significant for improving students' performance.

Secondly, the insignificant impact of low verbal interaction can be explained by their inability to sustain active involvement on the side of the students and by their high effectiveness in encouraging passivity. However, few studies indicated that medium and low verbal interaction were significant (Retallick & Butt, 2004; Tambaya, 2008), although these studies lack intervention fidelity to prove the most effective.

Thirdly, finding reveals that there was a significant difference in terms of academic performance between students taught biology using high verbal interaction and those taught using low verbal interaction ($t = 8.14$; $p\text{-value} < 0.05$), in favor of those taught using high verbal interaction. As discussed above,

high verbal interaction of collegiality entails 70% of student involvement while low verbal interaction involves 30% of participation, suggesting a wider gap of active participation. For this reason, students exposed to high verbal interaction of collegiality tend to be geared towards classroom activities, which in turn improve their performance. There was paucity of research evidence examining significant difference between high and low verbal interactions. Few studies that were found supported the finding of the study by indicating significant difference in the achievement of students exposed to different levels of verbal interaction, with high level favoring student achievement over medium and low verbal interactions (Tambaya, 2008; Usendia & Effiong, 2015).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the study concludes that of the two verbal interactions of collegiality, only high verbal interaction is significant for improving students' performance compared to lecture method, suggesting the need to allow students to dominate 70% of the classroom activities. High verbal interaction of collegial method is more significant for male students than female. However, intervention fidelity needs to be enforced to actively involve female

students who tend to be dominated by male students, thereby widening the gender gap towards science. High verbal interaction is more significant for improving students' performance than low verbal interaction, confirming the need to implement a more active teaching approach that involve high collaboration. Overall, collegial method is more beneficial than lecture method in terms of students' performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since only high level of verbal interaction is significant for improving student performance, Biology teachers should implement high level of verbal interaction to allow 70% of participation among students. Such participation however, should be implemented with exactitude to prove the most effective.
2. Since there was no significant difference and almost equal performance in students taught biology in both low verbal interaction and lecture method, research needs to be conducted to find out which method should be most recommended

3. Continuous teacher professional support through refresher courses, workshop training seminars and direct classroom support by fellow teachers and school administrators should be promoted and maintained to encourage effective verbal interaction.

Limitations of the Study

The following are notable limitations of the study;

1. Using only three schools in the study limits the scope on generalization.
2. Schedules for meeting with teachers for training posed a great challenge because times of meetings were overshadowed with other school's events. The schools used for this study were all public schools. The results may look different if private schools are involved. This factor may also affect generalization of the study.
3. Some principals were a bit skeptical about the study. They felt it was disrupting lesson and so did not give maximum cooperation as expected.

Contribution to Knowledge

This research discovered that:

1. The use of collegial teaching and Collegiality of teachers will provide practical tools for new teachers and administrators such as developing lesson plans, class organization, and

practice inclusiveness during lesson delivery, lesson observation, quality feedback and effective support before, during and after lesson.

2. The study in general has added literature to existing literatures.
3. Manual/model lesson plans that have been used for this research are sure to develop professional skills in teaching.
4. This study has helped Teachers' collegiality to widen the scope of teaching that is result oriented. Teachers should now go into the class with confidence knowing that they are not alone but other teachers are always around to support and guide.
5. The concept of teacher professional development is better undertaken and seen as something not far from the teacher since teachers are no longer isolated in the classroom but should conduct activities together which will help acquire and apply knowledge, skills and abilities to reach organizational goals.
6. Teachers who have learned to work together, become more flexible, more efficient and developed a sense of self efficacy. Collegially has helped teachers become committed do their job, assumed responsibilities beyond what was required of them, and increased motivation in teaching. Teachers got prepared well before

going to the class to teach.

7. Students are freely engaged/involved, knowing the roles to play to learn better.
8. The study also realized that effective interaction helped students to encourage joint projects, develop social skills, leadership roles, self-esteem, confidence and good team spirit with the use of collegial teaching method.

Suggested Areas for further study

1. Another study can be conducted to investigate teacher preparedness towards implementing collegial method of teaching.
2. A comparative analysis can be conducted to compare the impact of cooperative learning with collegial teaching.
3. In order to actually determine the impact of collegial method, a longitudinal analysis can be conducted to track students performance in a collegial classroom.
4. Studies on non-verbal teacher-student interaction need to be researched on since this study was done using levels of verbal interaction.
5. Similar studies should be carried in other subjects like Chemistry, physics, mathematics at the Senior Secondary School level.
6. The same study should be replicated at

the primary school level to compare results and come up with better approach to teaching science for better performance

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